

Anti-inflammatory property of colchicine – a boon to treat SARS-CoV-2

Shambho S.Samajdar^{1*}, Shrestha Dutta², Anwesha Behera², Oyendrilla Mitra², Ishanee Das Sharma², Mohojit Chakraborty¹

¹*Department of Pharmacology, School of Tropical Medicine, Kolkata*

²*Department of Biotechnology, Amity University Kolkata*

Email : shamboo_sa2001@yahoo.com

An effective treatment for SARS-CoV-2 was urgently required to reduce the mortality rate. The pathophysiology of SARS-CoV-2 has close link with aggressive lung disorders. A novel approach can be Colchicine. It invariably decreases pulmonary complexities, showing antimitotic action, causing metaphase arrest by inhibiting microtubule and spindle formation and is effective in reducing granulocyte migration, ultimately reducing inflammation. For this systemic review, papers were searched using the search engines like PubMed, NCBI and WebMD. The keywords used were – inverse probability, propensity score weighing, colchicines, SARS-CoV-2 and 7-point conventional scale. The papers searched were used for this retrospective study. In this systematic review by using propensity score analysis, it was observed that colchicine administration is related with decline in mortality and increased the clinical advancement in patients infected with Covid-19. Hence colchicine might be a beneficial drug likewise to treat a potential resurgence of SARS. Colchicine is related with decreased mortality and speeds up recuperation in COVID-19 patients. This supported the reasoning for current bigger randomized controlled preliminaries testing the safety/efficacy profile of colchicine in COVID-19 patients.

Keywords: Colchicine, SARS-CoV-2, Inverse probability, colchicine against covid-19.